

E-Commerce Platform & Fashion: Bhavana.com

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Abstract– This investigation focuses on the variables influencing visitors to e-commerce websites. It also examines Bhavana's performance in the fashion industry on the e-commerce platform. A method for online shopping that enables customers to place orders for products and/or services from a store that welcomes both walk-in and online customers. An online display of the order cutoff time and the associated delivery window for the client-specified details is provided by the online shopping system. When the customer submits a purchase order for an item before the order cutoff time, the system acknowledges their submission. The client's credit supplier is not paid by the online buying system until the item.

Keywords:- Bhavana, E-commerce, Factors, Online Shopping, Customer, Services;

I. INTRODUCTION

Although online buying is becoming more and more common, the idea of e-commerce was first presented in the 20th century. E-commerce has gained notoriety among visitors due to: Comfort Vacuity, more offers, a large selection of items, individualized care, and reduced prices.

➤ *E-commerce in India:*

The introduction of e-commerce has transformed Indian retail practices, particularly in light of the nation's internet usage and rapid expansion. Furthermore, a robust foundation was required for the formation of e-commerce in the request due to the shift in consumer buying patterns since the epidemic and the growing share of the organized sector within retail requests. With over 1.4 billion people on the planet and a rapidly rising level of frugal living, it is predicted that by 2027, there will be 427 million internet buyers. As a result, it is predicted that by 2030, the burgeoning e-commerce industry would be valued over 350 billion US dollars.

In addition to rising disposable income, the main reasons why the majority of consumers choose online buying are convenience and shifting cultural norms. Everything can be delivered with the push of a button, sometimes even in 10 seconds, including groceries and other necessities, especially for customers who reside in urban regions. Among the wellknown domestic quick commerce brands that offer efficient delivery services are Zepto, Zomato, and Swiggy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Myntra:*

An Indian e-commerce fashion company specializes in selling things related to clothing, apparel, footwear, beauty, and cosmetics. moment's reputable Flipkart became the parent company of the fashion e-commerce company Myntra in May 2014. In February 2007, Vineet Saxena, Ashutosh Lawania, and Mukesh Bansal invented it. Via its online platform, the fashion e-commerce company Myntra offers its drug users a variety of Internet-based services.

These services give drug users access to authentic products from vibrant lifestyle and fashion businesses, such as clothing, accessories, and shoes. Drug users have the option to purchase products on the platform using a variety of payment methods, such as cash on delivery, credit cards, debit cards, net banking, and UPI payments.[1]

➤ *Benefits of Myntra Include:*

- Time savings while shopping online
- Organizing finances and records is simple , and
- A variety of payment options • You may get stylish deals on Myntra.
- There are reduction tickets available.
- Shipping is free.

B. *Flipkart:*

In October of 2007, two former Amazon employees and IIT Delhi grads, Sachin [HYPERLINK "https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sachin_Bansal"](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sachin_Bansal) and Binny Bansal, launched Flipkart in Mumbai.

➤ *Headquarter:*

Karnataka, India's Bengaluru. Without a doubt, Flipkart is the most well-liked and extensive online buying destination in India. They provide a wide range of details in multiple sequences. There doesn't seem to be another Indian ecommerce site with as many different product categories offered for sale. Due to its partnerships with numerous shipping providers, Flipkart is able to provide prompt delivery of its details to a wide range of mature geographic locations. Furthermore, the delivery service continues to uphold a high standard of professionalism.[2]

C. *Amazon:*

Amazon.com is a multinational technology company based in the United States that specializes in digital streaming, artificial intelligence, online advertising, cloud computing, and one-stop shopping.

On July 5, 1994, Jeff Bezos launched Amazon from his Bellevue, Washington, garage. Since all of the stylish designs are arranged into a convenient digital storefront, Amazon is a great place to get them. You can also take advantage of the simple free shipping and free return policy that Amazon upholds for many of its products.

Amazon's fashion order is constantly streamlined to incorporate the newest trends, which are made quickly available to customers, making it faster than ever. Customers now have complete access to a particular style at their fingertips, so they don't need to stay months to enjoy it. With the help of the incredibly stoner-friendly Amazon app, visitors of all ages can easily locate what they need.

Amazon Style provides the same excellent prices as Amazon.com, along with the convenience of viewing and trying on specific items.

The following are some of the ways we've simplified security, both online and in-store:

- Find in-store and purchase online. Apart from the extensive range of details that guests can purchase in-store at Amazon Style, they can easily locate and safeguard additional styles on the internet.
- After you exit the store, continue your shopping. Details examined at Amazon Style are conveniently saved in the Amazon Shopping app, which makes it simple to revisit and make a purchase later or effortlessly locate additional details online from the new brands found in the store.
- Try on in-store, protect millions of personal details online. Visitors can order delivery to Amazon Style, view millions of garment details on Amazon.com, and try on items in a fitting room. If an item is not perfect, guests can return it in-store, and we'll take care of the rest.[3]

D. *Nykaa:*

Nykaa is an e-commerce company that sells directly to consumers (D2C) and uses a force-based approach. The business buys a wide range of goods from various product categories. These are supplied straight from the producers. It

keeps them in storage facilities located in Bangalore, Delhi, and Mumbai.

These locations allow for efficient delivery to both visitors and Nykaa stores. Nowadays, consumers have the option to purchase their preferred makeup products in-person or online. However, that has nothing to do with the Nykaa business model. This is merely a moisturizer for the popularity of the cosmetics line.

There are a number of unique products only found on Nykaa that cannot be found on any other e-commerce website. This has aided Nykaa in developing a USP and setting itself apart from competitors.

In addition to its own house brand, Nykaa Cosmetics, the exclusive product line also includes other high-end beauty and wellness items.

It is continuously refining its digital platform to ensure future inflexibility as well as to meet current challenges. The company's data team can provide dynamic, hyperactive, and individually tailored client gestures throughout their platform journeys by leveraging vast amounts of data.[4] The following factors help Nykaa become a household name in the ornamental assiduity:

- Marketing strategy;
- Omnichannel customer experience; and
- Customer-focused service and product.

➤ *Features:*

- Simple Login;
- Sludge Search
- Similar Outcome Appearance
- Simple Payment
- Summaries
- Order Monitoring
- Simple Returns

E. *AJIO:*

Completely redesigned, AJIO made its debut at Lakme Fashion Week on April 1, 2016, and its main office is in Bangalore, Karnataka, India. One of Reliance Industry's initial forays into e-commerce was Ajio. They offered a huge selection of clothing, accessories, and footwear when they first launched the app. Mukesh Ambani invented AJIO, an attachment company of Reliance Retail. Nair Vineeth is currently Ajio's CEO (chief executive officer).

AJIO is a lifestyle and retail brand that is the best place to shop for the most stylish and carefully curated fashion styles at the most affordable prices.

Through these services, drug users can purchase stylishly priced original products such as clothing, footwear, colorful fashion items, and electronic results for men, women, and children. Drug users can purchase goods via the platform by using one of the many payment methods that AJIO offers.[5]

➤ *Benefits of AJIO Listed Below:*

- Offers premium international label products
- Offers a variety of payment options
- Provides a wardrobe full of indie and ethnic clothing
- Offers coupons and discounts
- Saves money and time
- The Recharge offer by AJIO

F. Meesho:

The Indian business Fashnear Technologies Private Limited owns the e-commerce site Meesho. It's an online company that helps vendors, resellers, and customers conduct business; it mainly relies on third-party social media sites like Facebook and Instagram. IIT Delhi alums Vidit Aatrey and Sanjeev Barnwal founded Fashnear Technologies Private Limited in July 2015 as an on-demand fashion product delivery service similar to Swiggy, but for original retail stores. The beginning fell short. The authors' plan to relaunch the platform as Meesho, which would allow resellers to ship across the nation using social media platforms as marketing tools, was hatched in 2016. Both iOS and Android users can download the Meesho app. Anyone who is alive can create a Meesho account. After that, he or she is best suited to provide links to social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, and Whatsapp. Meesho handles online payments, product supervision, and real-time updates when a customer purchases a product.[6]

➤ *Meesho Offers:*

- Megahit items at the lowest costs;
- Chic quality with a simple return policy;
- Doorstep delivery throughout India
- COD & Online Payment Choices

G. Snapdeal:

Indian e-commerce startup Snapdeal is based in New Delhi. In February 2010, Rohit Bansal and Kunal Bahl invented it. On February 4, 2010, Snapdeal was launched as a platform for daily deals. In October 2011, the company went online. Snapdeal's mission is to enable Indian families to realize their dreams by providing them with stylish, affordable goods. Snapdeal has modified its business strategy recently. As of July 21, 2021, the e-commerce company has reversed its business model and begun focusing on value-conscious consumers. The business will now cater to a cult of customers who think that the reasonably priced line of goods offers better value than highend brands. Snapdeal spent eight to ten weeks refining its new, sophisticated look before launching it. To provide visitors with an even better stoner experience, improvements have been made to the desktop and mobile apps' enhanced stoner interfaces. In addition to improved features, customer satisfaction is prioritized.[7]

➤ *Some of the Features Include:*

- Content is categorized based on intent
- Product information is more easily recognizable
- All the information needed to make decisions can be accessed in a single view.

H. Shoppers Stop:

K Raheja Corp. owns the Shoppers Stop department store chain in India. In 40 Indian metropolises, there are 86 stores selling clothing, accessories, handbags, shoes, jewellery, spices, cosmetics, home furnishings, beauty products, and scenery items.

2008 saw the launch of an online store with delivery to all of India's major cities, and in 2016 a smartphone app.

Shoppers Stop has a seasoned and competent platoon that adheres to top-notch procedures and systems. The employees have a strong desire to provide their guests with a fashionable shopping experience. From a single store in 1991 to the biggest chain of department stores in India today, Shoppers Stop's growth can be attributed to this vision. At Shoppers Stop, our mission is to provide customers with an amazing shopping experience while establishing benchmarks for success.[8] It offers:

- Easy shopping
- Safe online shopping
- A wide selection of brands and products.
- Free Exchanges.
- 100% Genuine

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Numerous websites exist on the internet that provide a range of products and services, such as shoes, clothing, sunglasses, and more, for consumers to search and purchase online.

Additionally, the internet offers some services, such as online bill payment and transportation ticket reservation. We're investigating the issue this investigation looks at, which is consumers' perceptions of online shopping.

However, there are still a number of factors that discourage consumers from engaging in online shopping. For example, some consumers refuse to participate in online shopping for legitimate reasons, such as their dissatisfaction with the inferior quality of products they purchase online and their lack of confidence.

Furthermore, this research delves into the ways in which social factors impact consumers' purchase intentions when they shop online, as well as the location of those intentions.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Regardless of their geographical location or time difference, Bhavana's online platform for grounded e-commerce is an excellent means of connecting merchandisers and guests to make safe and efficient purchases. The largest selection of fashion and lifestyle products can be found at Bhavana. Merchandisers can list their products on the store's roster, allowing customers to peruse and select items that

catch their eye. The specified information might be gathered in a shopping wain.

The information in the shopping basket will be shown as an order at checkout. At that point, more data will be required in order to close the deal. Typically, the client will be prompted to provide payment details, such as a credit card number, and to fill out or select a billing address, shipping address, and shipping option. Additionally, the dealer packs the item.

Fig 1 Customers can Monitor Product Details

V. RESULT & CHALLENGES

A. Results:

Any e-commerce operation can use this operation. Because it makes use of the GUI provided in the stoner dialog, it is simple to use. We hand out stoner-friendly defenses. The system is user-friendly and interactive, making online shopping a fun pastime for drug users. It has undergone extensive testing and enforcement.

B. Challenges:

- Cooperation with online browsers such as Mozilla Firefox, Internet Explorer, and so forth.
- Developing the operation using a tiered strategy to provide justification for it.
- Gaining knowledge of new technologies, such as the Ajax toolkit controls and the drag-and-drop gesture in JavaScript.

- Getting a real-time experience is the main goal of this design.
- Study up on new technologies.

VI. CONCLUSION

The objective of "Online Shopping" is to offer a web-based application that facilitates product viewing, searching, and selection. The user can easily and conveniently search for products using the search engine's interactive feature, which allows the user to refine the products that are displayed based on their input. After that, the user can see every product's full specification. In addition, they have the ability to write and read their own product reviews. Ajax components could be used to prevent annoying post-backs and make the application interactive. It would be simple to use thanks to the drag and drop feature.

➤ *Future Scope:*

In the future, the following actions are possible.

- It is possible to expand the current system to enable users to register and add items to wish lists.
- Users have the option to sign up for price alerts, which would allow them to get notifications when a product's price drops below a specific threshold.
- The shopping cart process is the only function of the current system. It can be expanded to include a simple checkout procedure.
- Users have the option to save multiple shipping and billing addresses. They can choose their shipping and billing details using the drag and drop feature during the checkout process.

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